

Salt tectonics in Arabia Terra bulged craters? Hints from geological mapping, structural analysis and 3D geomodelling of the Crommelin Crater (Mars)

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Arabia Terra is a region of Mars that displays widespread and pervasive water interaction and possibly even fluid resurgence within impact craters. This is testified by light-toned fine layers (informally named ELDs), small spring mounds/mud volcanoes, and sulphate-bearing minerals(1–5). ELDs can be found both inside impact craters but also outside in the surrounding plateaus ranging from tens of meters up to km-thick sequences. Peculiar geometries of these layered sequences have been identified at places(2). Crommelin, a 90 km-wide crater, presents an elliptic bulge of 50x30 km with widespread ELDs in its surroundings that appear slightly tilted and folded (4). We produced a geological and structural map (1:160.000), on a mosaic of CTX stereo DTMs (18m grid size) and a seamless controlled mosaic of CTX orthoimages at 6 m/pixel obtained with ISIS3 and ASP (6, 7).

The stratigraphic sequence derived from the geologic mapping evidenced that the bulge occupies a lower stratigraphic position than the surrounding folded ELDs, which appear to be draping the bulge itself. The structural mapping highlighted the presence of at least two folding events in the ELD unit: km-size symmetric folds are visible in the western sector, whereas more pronounced NW-verging asymmetric folds are present in the NW sector. The Southern part presents elliptical basins with fine concentric stratification that were previously interpreted as desiccation ponds (4). However, from the structural analysis on the contrary they appear perfectly coherent with a dome and basin interference folding pattern, with major axis concentric to the bulge and the minor radial to it. A similar pattern is visible on the northern sector on the opposite side of the crater, partially obliterated by the ejecta of a nearby impact crater. The structural setting and fold patterns were modelled in 3D MOVE, using 21 cross sections perpendicular to the folding both on the western (11) and southern sectors (10). Using continuous strata banks as markers, we interpolated them and reconstructed the subsurface with 3D meshes representing the folded strata. The 3D reconstruction confirms the structural interpretation of two interacting folds systems that can be explained with a long-lasting uplift of a buried diapiric body in correspondence of the bulge after the deposition of the surrounding ELDs giving origin to the identified deformation patterns.

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